

dihydrazide the curve is shifted by 2.17 for 40% reaction. The shift corresponds to $k_1 = 6.76 \times 10^{-8} \text{ min}^{-1}$ which has been found to be similar to that of $k_1 (6.765 \times 10^{-8} \text{ min}^{-1})$ obtained by Swain's time-ratio method. This technique besides determining rate constant, indicates that the reaction studied is consecutive reaction.

The reaction between succinic acid dihydrazide and hexacyanoferrate(III) was investigated in the temperature range 30–50°. The values of energy of activation, enthalpy of activation, entropy of activation and frequency factor were found to be 39.97 kJ mol⁻¹, 37.38 kJ mol⁻¹, -40.89 e.u. and $2.1 \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$ respectively.

The variation of concentration of potassium sulphate showed a positive salt-effect indicating that the reaction may involve the species of the same charge or a charged species and neutral molecule and which should correspond to a negative entropy change⁷.

Different sets of the reaction mixtures containing known excess of hexacyanoferrate(III) over succinic acid dihydrazide were kept at 35° in presence of 1×10^{-4} NaOH for 48 h. The amounts of hexacyanoferrate left in all the cases were consistent with the stoichiometric equation. It is observed that one mole of substrate required four moles of oxidant. The malonic acid, nitrogen and the hydrogen are the main products of the reaction. The acid was detected by tlc while the nitrogen by Dumas method.

At constant OH⁻ the plot of $(-\frac{dc}{dt})^{-1}$ against 1/[sub-

strate] gave a straight line satisfying Michaelis-Menten type⁸ reciprocal relationship and indicating the probability of the complex formation between oxidant and substrate prior to the rate-determining step.

It was observed that the rate increases significantly with an increase in alkali concentration. Alkali dependence of oxidation process clearly indicates that the oxidation of dihydrazide takes place through an intermediate anion of the substrate formed by reaction with hydroxyl ion⁹.

Mechanism: A scheme for the oxidation of succinic acid dihydrazide by alkaline hexacyanoferrate has been proposed (Scheme 1).

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Photoirradiation of some 3-Benzyloxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyrans

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FLAVONE (2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran) is known to photosensitise the *cis-trans* isomerisation of stilbene¹. Since various derivatives of flavone occur in plants and are exposed to light, their acting as photodynamic-transferring agents is not remote². Our interest in the photochemistry of flavones³ and related compounds prompted us to study the effect of light on 3-benzyloxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyrans (1–3).

- 1, 4, 5; R=F
2, 6, 7; R=Cl
3, 8; R=H

Scheme 1

6-Chloro-3-(*p*-fluorobenzyloxy)-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran (**1**; R=F) was irradiated in C₆H₆-solvent through pyrex-filter under water cooling. A tlc analysis (benzene-EtOAc, 19 : 1) of the intense yellow reaction mixture (Scheme 1) after 90 min, revealed the complete disappearance of the starting material (**1**). A column chromatographic separation provided **4** (6%), m.p. 221–22°, $\nu_{\max}$ 1 640 cm⁻¹, M^+ 380/352 and **5** (14%), m.p. 230–31°, $\nu_{\max}$ 1 635 cm⁻¹, M^+ 378/380. To achieve the complete separation of the two tetracyclic compounds, **4** and **5**, due to their very close R_f values, it became obligatory to do repeated column chromatography and preparative tlc (silica gel).

The mass spectroscopic and elemental analyses indicated compound **4** to be isomeric with **1**. Its structure became evident from the 100 MHz pmr (FT) spectrum (Table 1) which showed the absence of 3-*O*-CH₂- (δ 5.06). The observance of J_{H_4a, H_5} 10.2 Hz suggests that H_{4a} and H₅ are *trans*-axially disposed with the larger group (C₆-phenyl) present in the favourable ψ -equatorial position. From the inspection of the models, H₄ seems to lie in the shielding zone of C₆-phenyl group, thereby making it to appear at higher field than H₅. Amongst the olefinic protons, the most downfield position of H₁ (δ 6.74) can be linked to its conjugation with C=O group. The relative position of H₃ and H₄ was confirmed when the irradiation of the resonances due to the latter modified the multiplet due to former to a broad singlet which had the same shape as that of the signal assigned to H₁. Mass spectral fragmentation (Table 1 and Scheme 2) lent further credence to the structure **4**; two retro-Diels Alder (RDA)

Scheme 2

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1–8†

Compd.	M.p. °C	δ
1	125–27	5.05 (2H, s, OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ F), 6.87 (2H, m, H _{3''} , H _{5''}), 7.15–7.50 (6H, m, H _{6'} , H _{8'} , H _{4''} , H _{5''} , H _{2''} , H _{6''}), 7.57 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 9 and 2 Hz, H ₇), 7.85–7.95 (2H, m, H _{2'} , H _{6'}), 8.20 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2 Hz, H ₈)
4 ^a	221–22	2.90–3.15 (2H, m, H ₃), 3.20–3.50 (1H, m, H _{4a}), 4.63 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 10.2 Hz, H ₅), 5.21 (ddd, ^{**} J_{H_4, H_8} 9.3 Hz, <i>J</i> _{allylic} 1.9 Hz, $J_{H_4, H_{4a}}$ 3.8 Hz, H ₄), 5.87 (1H, m, H ₃), 6.74 (1H, br s, H ₁), 6.99–7.16 (2H, t, <i>J</i> 8 Hz, H _{3'} , H _{5'}), 7.23–7.46 (3H, m, H _{2'} , H _{6'} , H ₁₁), 7.53–7.62 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 9.2 and 2.4 Hz, H ₁₀), 8.20 (d, <i>J</i> 2.4 Hz, H ₈)
5	231–32	6.32 (1H, s, H ₈), 6.95–7.15 (3H, m, H _{4'} , H _{3'} , H _{5'}), 7.20–7.72 (6H, m, H _{2'} , H ₃ , H ₁₀ , H ₁₁ , H _{2'} , H _{6'}), 7.85–7.92 (1H, m, H ₁), 8.24 (d, <i>J</i> 2 Hz, H ₈)
2	145–47	5.10 (2H, s, <i>o</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ Cl), 7.20 (4H, s, <i>o</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ Cl), 7.35–7.50 (4H, m, H ₈ , H _{3'} , H _{4'} , H _{5'}), 7.55–7.60 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 9 and 2 Hz, H ₇), 7.85–7.95 (2H, m, H _{2'} , H _{6''}), 8.20 (d, <i>J</i> 2 Hz, H ₈)
6 ^b	223–26	2.79–3.01 (2H, m, H ₃), 3.20–3.44 (1H, m, H _{4a}), 4.63 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 10.2 Hz, H ₅), 5.11–5.22 (1H, m, H ₄), 5.70–5.96 (1H, m, H ₃), 6.76 (1H, br s, H ₁), 7.24–7.43 (5H, m, H ₁₁ , C ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ Cl), 7.55 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 9 and 2.4 Hz, H ₁₀), 8.24 (d, <i>J</i> 2.4 Hz, H ₈)
7	210–13	6.32 (1H, s, H ₈), 7.05–7.54 (8H, m, H ₃ , H ₄ , H ₁₁ , C ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ Cl), 7.55 (1H, dd, <i>J</i> 9 and 2 Hz, H ₁₀), 7.82–7.88 (1H, m, H ₁), 8.20 (d, <i>J</i> 2 Hz, 1H, H ₈)
3	92–93	5.10 (2H, s, <i>o</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅), 7.05–7.66 (10H, m, H ₇ , H ₈ , H _{3'} , H _{4'} , H _{5'} , <i>o</i> -CH ₂ -C ₆ H ₅), 7.85–7.95 (2H, m, H _{2'} , H _{6'}), 8.17 (d, <i>J</i> 2 Hz, H ₈)
8	222–23	6.32 (1H, s, H ₈), 7.0–7.15 (1H, m, H ₄), 7.35 (5H, s, C ₂ -C ₆ H ₅), 7.45–7.60 (4H, m, H ₃ , H ₃ , H ₁₀ , H ₁₁), 7.90 (1H, m, H ₁), 8.23 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2.5 Hz, 1H, H ₈)
4 ^a	m/z 380/382 (45), 379/381 (51), 378/380 (5), 283/285 (8), 272/274 (3), 271/273 (7), 256/258 (12), 243/245 (14), 226 (2), 223 (9), 215/217 (11), 196 (35), 154/156 (9), 126/128 (23), 109 (100), 105 (15), 102 (5).	
6 ^b	m/z 396/398/400 (28), 395/397/399 (31), 394/396/398 (6), 283/285 (5), 272/274 (2), 271/273 (5), 256/258 (9), 243/245 (14), 242/244 (15), 239/241 (9), 215/217 (12), 212/214 (15), 154/156 (8), 126/128 (12), 125/127 (100), 105(12), 102 (6).	

†All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

*H₃ and H₄ may be exchanged.***J* values were found through decoupling experiments.

fragments were observed at m/z 154/156 and 226 (Scheme 2). The base peak interestingly was observed at m/z 10³ which could originate from a hydrogen rearranged ion possessing structure 10. This rearrangement found corroboration from the fact that mass spectra of 4 and 1 had many ions in common. The envisaged loss of two hydrogens from M^+ led to an ion 9, which further fragmented in the manner as found for the photoproduct 5. The structure of 5 was deduced as follows. The mass spectroscopic data showed that its formation involved the loss of two mass units from 1 and RDA fragments were present at m/z 154/156 and 224. The molecular ion (M^+ , 378/380) here was found to be the base peak. A comparison of the pmr spectra of 1 and 5 reveals that the region between δ 7.8–7.95 (H_a , H_b) integrating for two protons for 1 had only one proton in the spectrum of 5 and the singlet at δ 5.06 ($2 \times H$) in the former was replaced by a singlet at δ 6.32 ($1 \times H$) in the latter. It was suggestive enough that in the photoconversion $1 \rightarrow 5$, it is only H_a , or H_b , (both are chemically equivalent) and $o\text{-CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{R}$ participated. A DDQ treatment of 4 in refluxing benzene provided 5.

The photolysis of 2 ($R=\text{Cl}$) also furnished two compounds (6 and 7). But 3 under the same conditions gave only 8. All our attempts to isolate a dihydro derivative (corresponding to 4 or 6) during photolysis of 3 proved abortive, though no particular reason for such behaviour can be assigned.

The molecular changes and cyclodehydrogenations involved in the photoreactions of the benzopyrans (1–3) may be explained in terms of the proximity of 3-benzyloxy group to $\text{C}=\text{O}$ of the pyrone moiety. Under the photolytic conditions, the excited $\text{C}=\text{O}$ abstracts a hydrogen from 3- $O\text{-CH}_2\text{-}$, through a six-membered transition state, yielding a 1,4-diradical⁴ which then ends up in products (4–8).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Beckman IR-20, NMR Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz, CDCl_3 , TMS internal standard) and JNM FX-100 FT, JMS-D-300S spectrometers were used. Petroleum ether used refer to the fraction having b.p. 60–80°.

The 3-benzyloxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyrans (1–3) were prepared starting from 5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CHO}$ and NaOH, followed by cyclisation ($\text{NaOH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$)⁵ and benzylation ($\text{ClCH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-R}/\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{acetone}$).

Photolysis of benzopyrans: The benzopyran (1; 1.10 g) dissolved in thiophene-free benzene (200 ml) was photolysed (90 min) in a water-cooled pyrex glass immersion well with 200 W Hg vapour lamp. The dark yellow photolysate on evaporation (reduced pressure) and column chromatography on silica gel (30 g) with eluent benzene-petroleum

ether 7 : 3 and 4 : 1 gave 4 and 5 respectively. The compounds were purified through silica gel column (C_6H_6 -petroleum ether, 1 : 1) chromatography followed by preparative tlc (benzene-EtOAc, 98 : 2).

Dehydrogenation of 4: A benzene solution of 4 (0.1 g) was refluxed with DDQ (0.1 g) for 1 h. The resulting solution was percolated through a column of neutral Al_2O_3 and eluted with benzene to provide a solid, m.p. 230–31° (remained undepressed when mixed with 5).

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Lead Tetraacetate Oxidation of Steroidal Hydroxyketoximes

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IN continuation of our previous studies¹, we report here the lead(IV) acetate oxidation of steroidal hydroxyketoximes (1–3). The reaction of 3 β ,5-hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one-oxime (1)² afforded 3 β -acetoxycholest-4-en-6-one (4)³, 3 β -acetoxy-5-hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one (5)⁴ and 3 β ,5-hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-*N*-acetate (6). Under similar reaction conditions, 3 β -acetoxy-5-hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one-oxime (2)⁴ furnished compounds 4, 5 and 3 β -acetoxy-5-hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-*N*-acetate (7). 3 β -Chloro-5-hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one oxime (3)⁴ when treated with lead(IV) acetate yielded β -chlorocholest-4-en-6-one (8)⁵, 3 β -chloro-5-hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one-7 α -acetate (9) and 3 β -chloro-5-hydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-*N*-acetate (10). Structures of the compounds were supported by elemental analysis and spectral data (Table 1).